

Increased electroactive properties of poly(vinylidene fluoride) films by thermo-mechanical post-processing

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Abstract: Due to its outstanding electroactive properties, poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is widely used in the energy, electronic, and biomedical fields. In particular, the highly polar and electroactive β -phase obtained by low temperature solvent evaporation has numerous technological applications due to its piezo-, pyro- and ferroelectric properties, but typically presents a porous morphology. PVDF membranes were prepared by non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) from a dimethylformamide (DMF) solution, and post-processed by thermo-mechanical compression under varying temperature and pressure to produce solid films. The effect of these parameters on the morphology, β -phase content, thermal properties, crystalline phase content and piezoelectric response was evaluated. Thermo-mechanical treatment reduces porosity leading to a compact morphology, while also increases the β phase content and the degree of crystallinity. Also, it enhances the mechanical properties and increases the piezoelectric value. It is to notice that this simple processing method is compatible with the large-scale manufacturing of electroactive PVDF samples in an industrial setting.

1. Introduction

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), is a synthetic fluoropolymer composed of vinylidene fluoride monomers [1]. It possesses interesting properties like high chemical resistance, thermal stability and mechanical strength [1-3]. PVDF also belongs the group of smart materials since it has the ability to provide an active response in response to environmental variations, due to its piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties. PVDF and its co-polymers exhibit the highest piezoelectric response of all polymeric materials making it a perfect candidate for the production of sensors and actuators involving mechano-electric transduction [1, 3]. Sensing/actuating capabilities can be integrated and applied in a simple and low-cost way since it arises from PVDF's chemical structure and organization [1, 3].

Crystalline structure is the main parameter defining PVDF's piezoelectric properties. It is a semi-crystalline polymer exhibiting three main crystal structures, α , β and γ [1, 4]. α -phase is the most common and has a trans-gauche-trans-gauche (TGTG) orientation, meanwhile β -phase has an all trans (TTT) planar, and γ -phase trans-trans-trans-gauche (TTTG) conformation [4]. The fluoride's electronegativity when compared to hydrogen or carbon atoms implies that their relative orientation leads to a dipolar moment when oppositely orientated with respect to the carbon backbone chain [4, 5]. The β -phase's all trans orientation means a maximum dipolar moment with all the dipoles oriented in the same way thus maximizing the piezoelectric response, γ -phase also exhibits piezoelectric behavior although some cis groups promote a partial dipolar compensation and reduced response, all trans-gauche orientation in the α crystal promote the full dipole compensation in the crystalline unit cell thus eliminating all piezoelectric response [4, 5]. Rendering PVDF piezoelectric necessary for its electroactive applications, and many of the research around it is devoted to its promotion and enhancement. Inducting β -phase

has been extensively explored and can be achieved through various processing strategies [6]. Common processing techniques include heat annealing [7-9], electrical poling [10-12], filler addition [13-15], mechanical stretching [11, 16, 17], mechanical compression [18-20], electrospinning [21], melt electrowriting [22] or combinations of the above [14, 23, 24].

Non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) is a common method for the production of polymer membranes [25]. When a polymer solution is spread into a substrate and immersed in a non-solvent bath, an exchange between the solvent and non-solvent occurs, leading to the polymer's precipitation [26]. As a result, membranes produced by the NIPS method are asymmetrical with a porous layer formed on the side contacting the bath, caused by the solvent exchange, and a denser solid layer is formed on the side contacting the substrate [25, 26]. A variety of factors like the nature of the solvent and non-solvent, the solutions temperature, additives and exchange time can influence the resulting morphology and crystallization kinetics [27].

Processing PVDF from a polar solvent solution like dimethylformamide (DMF) or dimethylacetamide (DMA) at temperatures below 70 °C is known to induce β -phase crystallization [28, 29]. NIPS processing of PVDF allows for both conditions to be met [30, 31]. Other techniques like solvent casting also promote β -phase crystallization, although it is a slow process when compared to NIPS since PVDF cast membranes commonly take more than 24 hours to fully crystallize [31]. NIPS fast processing is thus better suited to industrial applications where time implies a big economic impact. Further, NIPS can be performed with materials that are affordable, accessible and easy to manipulate and dispose like water and ethanol [26, 32, 33]. NIPS techniques are among the most commonly used when a porous surface and high contact area are desirable, like in the case of membranes for exchange, filtration membranes or energy storage separation

[1, 31]. For other applications like sensors or actuators it can be a big drawback since it implies poor mechanical properties or difficult polarization procedures, among others [31, 34].

Film stretching is the most common post-treatment method for piezoelectricity dependent, hence high β -phase, applications [16, 17]. Films are initially heated to enhance polymer chain mobility and ductility and then stretched at high stretching ratios to effectively induce α to β -phase transformation [17]. A similar approach has been proposed, with polymer chain stretching being achieved by mechanical compression rather than direct stretching [18]. Both methods have proven effective in promoting β -phase re-crystallization, only the later has seldom been used and explored, despite posing several advantages. Mechanical compression is a simpler process, it is not limiting regarding the size of the sample than can be treated, and much easier to scale up, industrialize and automatize through the use of rollers. Contrary to film stretching, where film clamping occurs parallel/axially to chain elongation, compression is applied perpendicular to chain elongation, resulting in a much better process to apply in conjunction with an electric field, polarizing/orienting the polymer chains in order to further enhance the PVDF's piezoelectric macroscopic response.

By combining the NIPS process with mechanical compression post-processing, films with high β -phase content and electroactive properties can be produced in a simple and scalable process. This electroactive response originates in the dipolar structure of the polymer chains and the degree of crystalline ordering [35]. The goal of this work is the development of a method that takes advantage of the simplicity of the NIPS processing, able to simply produce porous membranes with high β -phase content, together with a post processing method able to improve its disadvantages like the poor mechanical properties, high heterogeneity and porosity. Resulting in a process suitable for the industrial

application/ production of electroactive PVDF films for sensing/actuating/energy harvesting applications. This approach, combining NIPS processing and mechanical compression post-processing has never been previously explored, nor has been any attempt to explain the mechanisms underlying the resulting changes in the sample's properties.

NIPS membranes are produced using an ethanol bath. Which were then post-processed by mechanical compression, at different temperatures (40 °C and 100 °C) and pressures (50 and 100 bar). The resulting films properties, including morphological, chemical, thermal, mechanical and piezoelectric, are presented and discussed.

2. Experimental

2.1. Membrane preparation

PVDF membranes were prepared by the NIPS method, adapted from the works of [26, 27]. Firstly, Solef® 6010 Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) (Solvay, Belgium), Melt Mass-Flow Rate (MFR) (230 °C/5.0 kg) of 4.0 to 8.0 g/10 min, was dissolved in N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (Fluka, Switzerland) to a concentration of 20% w/v under magnetic stirring at 60 °C. Once dissolved, the solution was spread over a glass plate with a casting knife with 750 µm spacing and immersed in an Ethanol (EtOH) (Scharlab, Spain) bath for 1 hour to remove the DMF and precipitate the PVDF, thus producing a membrane. Once precipitated, the membranes were submerged in an ultrapure H₂O bath for 24 hours to remove any DMF remnants. Freed from DMF, the membranes were directly frozen at -20 °C for 24 hours, after which they were dried under vacuum, directly from the freezer, at 40 °C for 24 hours. Dried membranes were ready to be used. Samples in this state will be referred from now on as NEAT.

2.2. Mechanical post-processing

NEAT PVDF membranes were post-processed by mechanical compression in a Gumix T0 – 250 / 20 apparatus. Membranes measuring approximately 40 x 40 mm² were sandwiched between two 70 × 70 × 2 mm³ poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) plates and compressed for 1 hour to form solid films. The press machine and PTFE plates were pre-heated for 1 hour before treatment while the film was used from room temperature. The influence of post-processing parameters was studied by applying two temperature and pressure settings, 40 and 100 °C, and 50 and 100 bar, respectively. These settings were combined originating 4 post-processing conditions/samples: 40 °C / 50 bar, 40 °C / 100 bar, 100 °C / 50 bar and 100 °C / 100 bar. 50 and 100 bar pressure in 40 mm² samples corresponds to an exerted force of 3.1 and 6.2 GN, respectively.

2.3. Characterization techniques

Morphological characteristics of PVDF films were assayed by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) in a Carl Zeiss Ultra 55 (Carl Zeiss, Germany). Images were collected at 1 kV beam intensity. Before their visualization, samples were gold sputter coated for 60 seconds under Argon atmosphere in a Bal-Tec SCD 005 (Bal-Tec, Liechtenstein) equipment to increase imaging acuteness and resolution. Dimensions were measured using the ImageJ image analysis software.

The vibrational spectra were obtained by Fourier-Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Infrared spectra were collected in a Bruker Alpha II (Bruker, USA) in the attenuated total reflectance mode (ATR) and collected after 128 scans at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution between 4000 and 400 cm⁻¹.

Thermal properties were assayed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in a Mettler Toledo Thermal Analysis System DSC 3 (Mettler Toledo, USA). Thermograms were

collected in the first scan from 30 to 200 °C at 20 °C / minute heat rate. Samples were cut into 5 mm diameter discs to perfectly fit the 40 µl aluminum pans.

A stress/strain mechanical analysis was performed in a Seiko Exstar 6000 with a TMA/SS6000 accessory (Seiko, Japan) stabilized by an Halcyonics MOD-1M Plus (Halcyonics, Germany) active vibration isolation system. Samples were cut into 3 × 17 mm strips and stretched from 0 to 500 µm at 25 µm/min at room temperature. In order to properly consider sample's variability, analysis was performed in triplicates.

The piezoelectric constant, $|d_{33}|$, of the films was measured with a Model 8000 (APC International, United States) set up. Before analysis the films were poled by corona discharge in a homemade apparatus. Films were cut into 1.5 cm² squares and pre-heated at 60 °C for 1 hour. Then, a corona discharge of 10 kV voltage under constant 20 µA current was applied for 1 hour at 120 °C. The samples were then cooled with the corona discharge still on and were removed once room temperature was reached [27].

3. Results

3.1. Morphology

FE-SEM allows the detailed visualization of the sample's morphological features and it was performed for NEAT and treated samples under various thermo-mechanical post-processing conditions, thus evidencing the consequent morphological changes evidenced in Figures 1 and 2. Changes in membrane thickness are displayed in Table 1. Sample thickness was the average value calculated from 10 measurements from 2 different places of the sample.

Upon mechanical compression sample thickness decreased from 202 to between 78 and 55 µm depending on the compression conditions. There is no correlation between each of the conditions and the thickness achieved. Among samples the thickness is very uniform with minimal standard deviation. Some differences occur between batches due to the

manual spread and dip of the NEAT membranes, these would not occur is performed in an automated industrial setting. Therefore, the developed post-processing method produced very uniform membranes with a maximum standard deviation of 4 μm .

Both the surface and transversal cuts were imaged, with the later providing details regarding variations in the internal microstructure and the former on the sample's surface. Morphological analysis of the NEAT samples reveals typical structures from NIPS produced PVDF membranes. Rounded spherulites are visible both on the surface Figures 1a and 1f and in the cross section, Figures 2a and 2f. Some micrometer-sized holes, are also visible on the surface and in the core of the sample, as a result of the growth of the dispersed polymer spherulites [36]. After post-processing, and independently of its conditions, the sample's open structure was largely reduced, and spherulite compression melting and recrystallization occurred, as discussed below in section 4. The reduction in the number of voids as well as spherulite deformation are better observed in the cross-section images, nevertheless it is also evident as in the surface images. On Figure 2j, partial spherulite fusion was observed. The temperature of 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was chosen to soften the sample without causing its fusion (PVDF T_m approx 160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) [37]. Spherulite fusion can only be explained by the energy transferred from the mechanical compression. The increased mechanical compression observed in Figure 4d, and later discussed in greater detail, further strengthens our observations. Mechanical strength is an indirect measurement of spherulite fusion since solid structures have higher mechanical strength. A correlation can be established between the structures in Figure1 and Figure2 and the mechanical behavior observed in Figure 4d.

Membrane porosity was indirectly calculated by comparing the volumes of NEAT samples with the volumes of compressed samples (post-treated samples were assumed to be compressed at 100%), by applying Equation 1,

$$P = 100 - \frac{V_c \times 100}{V_n} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where P represents the NEAT sample porosity and V_c and V_n the volumes of the compressed and uncompressed sample, respectively.

NEAT sample has an average porosity of $61 \pm 7\%$, with the NIPS processing method producing PVDF membranes with porosities between 55 and 70%.

Figure 1. FESEM upper surface images of the NIPS processed PVDF sample before and after compression treatment under various conditions. Scale bar 20 μm (a-e) and 2 μm (f-j).

Figure 2. FE-SEM cross-section images of PVDF NIPS membranes untreated and after post-treatment under various conditions. Scale bar corresponds to 20 μm (left) and 2 μm (right).

Table 1. PVDF Thickness of PVDF NIPS sample before and after mechanical compression with different conditions.

	NEAT	40 °C_ 50 bar	100 °C_ 50 bar	40 °C_ 100 bar	100 °C_ 100 bar
Thickness (μm)	202 ± 12	55 ± 1	78 ± 4	76 ± 1	65 ± 2

3.2. Electroactive β -phase content and thermal properties

FTIR analysis allows the identification of the chemical groups present in the sample through their corresponding infrared absorption energies/peaks. It has been extensively used for the identification and quantification of the PVDF's crystalline phases [5, 13, 38-40]. Since different crystalline structures correlate to specific absorption peaks [1], their relative percentage can be calculated by comparing the specific peak's intensities. Figure 3a shows the FTIR spectra for all samples. Since absorption peaks overlap in some regions, a spectra deconvolution must be performed in order to isolate the peaks of interest and correctly calculate the relative percentages of the various crystalline phases present, as presented in Figure S1 in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 3. a) FTIR Absorption spectra, b) DSC thermograms, c) DMA stress/strain graphs and d) modulus of the $|d_{33}|$ piezoelectric coefficient of the NIPS processed PVDF NEAT and the samples treated at different thermo-mechanical conditions.

As can be observed in the infrared spectra (Figure 3a), and is summarized in Table 2, most of PVDF's specific absorbance peaks are present in all samples independently of post-processing conditions. Although, the peaks at 614 and 795 cm^{-1} , α -phase specific, are visibly more intense in the NEAT sample and the bands at 1234 and 1276 cm^{-1} , corresponding to β and γ -phases, are noticeably more intense in the post-processed samples.

Table 2. FTIR absorption of PVDF's specific bands and corresponding chemical structures.

Crystalline structure	Characteristic bands (cm^{-1})	Chemical group
α -phase	614	CF_2
	763	CF_2
	795	CH_2
	975	CH
β -phase	1276	CF
γ -phase	840	CH_2
	1234	CF_2

The calculation of the electroactive, sum of $\beta + \gamma$ phases, and α phases relative percentages, can be performed by applying equation (2) [13],

$$F(\beta + \gamma) = \frac{A_{\beta+\gamma}}{\left(\frac{K_{\beta+\gamma}}{K_{\alpha}}\right)A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta+\gamma}} \quad (2)$$

where $F_{(\beta + \gamma)}$ represents the electroactive phase relative percentage, $A_{\beta + \gamma}$ and A_{α} the peak intensities at 840 and 766 cm^{-1} , respectively, and $K_{\beta + \gamma}$ and K_{α} the absorption coefficients of the corresponding bands with values of 7.7×10^4 and 6.1×10^4 cm/mol , respectively [13].

In order to discriminate between the electroactive phases, β and γ , and independently calculate their relative percentages the Equation (3) is applied [13],

$$F(\gamma) = F(\beta + \gamma) \times \left(\frac{A_{\gamma}}{A_{\gamma} + A_{\beta}}\right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where, $F_{(\gamma)}$ and $F_{(\beta + \gamma)}$ represent the crystal phases relative percentages, and $A_{(\gamma)}$ and $A_{(\beta)}$ the peak infrared absorption peak intensities measured at 1234 and 1276 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The relative percentages of the crystal phases present in sample are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystal phase percentages of the NIPS processed PVDF samples, NEAT and compressed at different conditions.

	Neat	40 °C 50 bar	100 °C 50 bar	40 °C 100 bar	100 °C 100 bar
F($\beta + \gamma$)	55	70	80	73	77
F(α)	45	30	20	27	23
F(β)	22	24	32	26	26
F(γ)	33	46	48	47	51

By analyzing Table 3, it is observed that the electroactive phase increased with the post-processing independently of the conditions, increasing from 55%, in the NEAT sample, to 80% in the 100 °C_50 bar sample as it depends on the crystallization temperature. An increase in the electroactive β and γ phases was observed after thermo-mechanical post-processing.

Among the post-processing conditions tested, temperature had a higher influence than pressure on the electroactive phase increase. This could be observed in all samples (Table 3), and mostly by the increase in γ -phase percentage and the decrease in α -phase. It seems that β -phase does not follow such clear behavior as other crystalline phases. Higher temperatures increase chain mobility thus facilitating the molecular rearrangement and promoting the crystallization of electroactive structures. Similarly, other means of increasing chain mobility promote the crystallization of these structures like processing from solution.

DSC thermograms allow the evaluation and comparison of the various sample's melting peaks and thermal transitions. Figure 3b shows the DSC thermograms of the different samples. The melting peaks of α , β , and γ phases overlap in the temperature range between 140 and 180 °C, roughly speaking. In the untreated sample, NEAT, containing a high fraction of α phase crystals, a single broad, exothermic peak appears. However, a second narrower peak clearly appears in the treated samples which overlaps with the main peak on the high temperature side. The overlap between the main peak and this second peak prevents a more detailed analysis to establish a correlation between the height of the peak and its position with the fraction of the different crystalline phases.

From the melting transition, the crystalline fractions of all samples can be compared. The sample's total crystalline percentage can be calculated from the corresponding thermogram's melting enthalpy by applying Equation (4) [13]:

$$X_c(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_s}{x\Delta H_\alpha + y\Delta H_\beta + z\Delta H_\gamma} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where, $X_c(\%)$ represents the crystalline percentage of the sample and ΔH_s , the melting enthalpy of the sample, $x\Delta H_\alpha$, $y\Delta H_\beta$ and $z\Delta H_\gamma$ the melting enthalpies of pure crystalline PVDF in the corresponding crystal phase, 93.07, 103.40 and 104.60 J/g [13], respectively, and x , y and z their relative percentages, as calculated from the FTIR experiments (Table 3).

Crystalline percentages for the untreated and treated samples are summarized in Table 4, together with the melting temperature and enthalpy. The melting temperature was only slightly affected by the post-treatment.

Table 4. Thermal characteristics and Young's modulus of the NIPS processed PVDF membranes, neat and after compression post-treatment.

	NEAT	40 °C 50 bar	100 °C 50 bar	40 °C 100 bar	100 °C 100 bar
T_m (°C)	172 ± 1	171 ± 1	170 ± 1	171 ± 1	170 ± 1
ΔH_s (J/g)	52 ± 1	64 ± 1	68 ± 1	62 ± 1	64 ± 1
X_c (%)	53 ± 1	63 ± 1	67 ± 1	61 ± 1	63 ± 1
E_a / Pa	1.07×10 ⁷ ± 2%	1.25×10 ⁸ ± 2%	1.94×10 ⁸ ± 2%	1.53×10 ⁸ ± 2%	2.62×10 ⁸ ± 2%

The crystallinity degree and the melting enthalpy represents the percentage of crystalline structures in the sample and the energy, normalized to mass, needed to melt one gram of sample, respectively. These parameters are interdependent since the melting enthalpy is the basis for the estimation/calculation of the sample's crystalline percentage.

There is a clear increase in the melting enthalpy with the compression treatment, between 10 and 14% (Table 4) although the influence of the thermo-mechanical treatment

conditions is small. The change in the crystalline fraction of the sample is parallel to the change in the melting enthalpy because besides the melting enthalpy of the α phase being somewhat lower than in the electroactive phases and the mechanical treatment decreases the α phase fraction, the influence of these factors in the calculation of the overall crystalline fraction is not relevant.

3.3. Mechanical properties

A stress/strain mechanical analysis, and calculation of the apparent Young's modulus were performed in order to assess the effects of the mechanical compression post-processing parameters on the sample's mechanical behavior. Figure 3c shows the DMA stress-strain curves for the NEAT and post-processed membranes. Table 4 shows the average Young's modulus of the different measurements. Since the samples do not exhibit perfectly linear elastic behavior, the apparent Young modulus was calculated according to equation (5) on the 0 to 1% deformation segment.

$$E_a = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

where, E_a represents the apparent Young's modulus, $\Delta\sigma$ the difference in stress between 0 and 1% tensile strain, and $\Delta\varepsilon$, the difference in tensile strain corresponding to 0 and 1% of the sample's original length.

Figure 3c and Table 4 show that post-processing had marked effects the sample's mechanical behavior independently of the treatment conditions. The Young's modulus increased from a minimum of 1065% to a maximum of 2346% when comparing the NEAT and treated samples.

Considering the four thermo-mechanical post-processing conditions tested, the temperature variation had a greater impact in the improvement of the mechanical properties than the increase in pressure. Using the 40 °C_50 bar sample as reference, the temperature increase promoted an increase in the Young modulus of 0.7×10^8 , while the pressure variation only increased it in 0.3×10^8 . Nonetheless pressure and temperature had a synergistic effect in improving the mechanical properties, the highest modulus was achieved when both parameters were increased together. The Young modulus increases 1.3×10^8 for the 100 °C_100 bar sample with respect to the 40 °C_50 bar sample, surpassing the sum of the differences observed when parameters were increased separately.

3.4. Electroactive response

Electroactive properties of the various samples were assayed through the direct measurement of the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} . Figure 3d) displays the modulus of the d_{33} values (the values are negative, as corresponding to PVDF) for all NIPS processed PVDF membranes. The d_{33} value is stable at least for over 1 month after the polarization process.

The compression post-processing demonstrated to be very efficient in increasing the piezoelectric performance of PVDF films independently of the conditions applied. d_{33} increased at least 5-fold independently of the processing conditions. A correlation between d_{33} and the post-treatment temperature cannot be drawn.

Neither the direct correlation between the sample porosity calculated at 3.1 and the electroactive response since this parameter is dependent on surface area and not overall porosity. Assuming the former from the latter would be incorrect since we cannot measure the sample deformation during analysis or the effective area of contact. Nonetheless

variations in contact area between samples are not enough to explain variations in d_{33} response up to 5-fold, much greater than differences in direct contact area.

The maximum d_{33} values achieved is very high for a pure PVDF sample. 4 pC/N is already considered an intense piezoelectric response [41]. Similar values of 14 pC/N were reached on spin coated and poled samples [42], and some authors managed to reach 21 pC/N after extensive optimization of the processing procedures [41] or multi-layered substrates (D). Literature cites higher values of 17.9 or 30 pC/N, although these are reached using doped composites [43] or mixed with piezoceramics [44] that by themselves reach much higher values, sometimes orders of magnitude, of up to 100 pC/N [44]. The achieved maximum d_{33} value of 13.6 pC/N is on par with the highest values achieved for pure PVDF samples.

4. Discussion

In the process of membrane formation by NIPS, the non-solvent, ethanol in our case, mixes with the DMF in which the PVDF is dissolved, changing the solubility parameter of the solvent. As a consequence, the PVDF precipitates crystallizing in the form of spherulites. Each spherulite grows from a crystallization nucleus through the diffusion of polymer chains that are incorporated into the growing border of the crystalline lamellae. The large amount of solvent present causes the polymer in solution to be diffused before the spherulites touch each other and thus the resulting microstructure consists of a disorderly agglomerate of spheres of about 2 μm in diameter. Interestingly, the size of these crystalline spheres is very uniform indicating that all the spherulites started their growth simultaneously. On the other hand, the fact that crystallization is initiated from randomly distributed nucleation points leaves voids with dimensions up to 20 μm , irregularly distributed both on the surface and in the interior of the sample. The

interconnection between the spherulites is very weak, which, together with the high porosity, translates to very poor mechanical properties, as can be seen in the Figure 3c stress-strain diagrams. The microstructure that can be observed in the cross section (Figure 2a, 2f) is very similar to that of the surface of the membrane, which is in direct contact with the solvent. The opposing surface, in contact with the support, exhibits a similar microstructure although with somewhat flattened spherulites by the contact with the glass. In PVDF's crystallization from solution, the polymer chains are highly mobile and this facilitates the relatively high, 22% (Table 3), proportion of all-trans, β -phase crystalline structures, which are preferred/favored by thermodynamic equilibrium criteria. There is also a relatively high proportion of γ phase and overall, slightly more than half of the crystals constitute the electroactive phases.

The thermo-mechanical treatment proposed in this work aims not only to compact the membrane structure, by reducing the space between the spherulites and therefore reducing the volume fraction occupied by the pores, but also to produce a recrystallization that increases the adhesion between the spherulites and the fraction of electroactive phases (Figure 3d). PVDF's melting temperature, the maximum of the endothermic melting peak in a DSC thermogram, sits at around 170°C (Figure 3b), with somewhat variable values depending on the predominant crystalline phase (Figure 3b). The compression treatment to which the membranes have been subjected was performed at 40 or 100°C. 40°C is far away from the temperature in which crystallization or melting in bulk PVDF occurs, but 100°C is in the range in which literature shows that uniaxial or biaxial deformation PVDF sheets, initially in α phase, recrystallize by deformation producing the β phase [17].

Figure 2 shows the morphology of membranes deformed by compression at 40 or 100°C and under pressures of 50 or 100 bar. In any of these treatments the thickness of the

sample goes from the initial 750 μm to barely 60 or 80 microns, indicating the extent of the NEAT NIPS membrane porosity. When compression is performed at 100°C it is observed, especially at 100 bar, that the surface spherulites partially melt with each other since micrometric holes between them can still be observed (Figure 1e and 1j). In the core of the sample the bonding between spherulites is not so clear but their deformation changes in the microspheres surface topography are observed (Figure 2e and 2j). The clearest indication that the deformation led to the melting of the crystalline structures, at least on the surface of the spherulites, and their subsequent recrystallization is in the fraction of electroactive phases present, in particular the γ phase, at the expense of the amount of α -phase crystals (Table 3). The mechanical energy transmitted through the compression process partly melts the original crystalline structure and induces the formation of new crystals during the deformation process [45], but the conditions under which crystallization occurs are very different from those under which the membrane was formed by NIPS, especially because of the absence of solvent and the mechanical stresses acting on the growing lamellae, this will lead to changes in the crystalline phases that are formed. The differences in the DSC thermograms between the compressed and untreated membranes also support that partial melting and recrystallization takes place during compression. The DSC thermogram of the NEAT sample shows a single endothermic peak covering a broad temperature interval (Figure 3b), the crystals in this sample have formed during solvent extraction by the non-solvent during membrane formation by NIPS. This may be a rather heterogeneous process leading to a broad distribution of crystal sizes. The narrow endothermic peak appearing in the DSC thermograms of the compressed samples (Figure 3b) could be ascribed to the melting of crystals formed during the recrystallization process under pressure that are the result of a more uniform

thermal and mechanical treatment throughout the sample, which explains why it is narrower, as well as corresponding to crystals richer in β and γ phases.

Microscopy images of sample compressed at 40°C seem to indicate that the effect is purely mechanical, not all spherulites change their morphology and a fraction of material retains the original microstructure. However, even at this low temperature, it is shown that recrystallization has occurred both by the increase in electroactive phases, although less than when compressed at 100°C, and in the shape of the DSC thermogram (Figure 3b). The sample temperature when compression is applied is an essential parameter in the process since it allows increased polymer chain mobility in the amorphous phase that sits in-between and separates the crystal lamellae [46].

It is interesting to note the difference between the stress-strain curves of samples subjected to the different treatments. Compression at 40°C results in a large increase in the stiffness of the sample with respect to the NEAT sample, as expected due to the large decrease in porosity, but deformation at 100°C produces even stiffer samples, which shows that there has been greater adhesion between the crystalline particles, giving more coherence to the microstructure of the sample, another indication that the recrystallization process mentioned above has taken place.

More important for the applications of these materials is the great improvement in the piezoelectricity of the samples obtained through the thermo-mechanical treatment. It is interesting to note that this type of processing can be scaled up to the industrial scale by processing through heated inter-roll compression, a method widely applied in the plastic processing industry.

A fact that is to be noticed is that the electroactive phase content, responsible for the PVDF's piezoelectric response, could not be directly correlated with d_{33} . 40 °C_50 bar and 40 °C_100 bar samples varied greatly in d_{33} piezoelectric response despite their

crystallinity and crystalline phases being very similar, which is related to the different mechanical properties and morphology. d_{33} measurements of the neat porous sample, with an electroactive phase content above 50% (Table 3) is 2 pC/N, mainly due to the highly porous morphology. With the post-processing of the samples (Figure 3d), there is a strong increase of the electroactive phase content above 70% (Table 3) and the $|d_{33}|$ values increase to values up to 13.6 pC/N. The post treatments improvement in d_{33} between the different samples cannot be solely justified by the increased electroactive phases, which is not very different between all post-processed samples. Thus, morphology also plays an important role in the piezoelectric response. In fact, based on the internal structure of the samples, it can be also electret contributions, i.e, charges in chemical bonds form molecular dipoles [35] due to charge addition with a re-orientation of the non-permanent dipole polarization [47].

The electroactive response in this type of samples is thus a complex behavior affected both by the piezoelectric response, related to the phase content and dipole orientation and characteristic of compact samples, and to the electret contributions, with a more complex dependence on sample's porosity.

5. Conclusions

Thermo-mechanical compression is an effective method for the post-processing of PVDF membranes in order to obtain films and simultaneously enhance their mechanical and electroactive properties. It is especially useful for electroactive applications, particularly as sensors/actuators by combining enhanced electroactive properties with morphological changes that can be taken to advantage, depending on the specific application.

Post-processing parameters include pressure (50 and 100 bar) and temperature (40 and 100 °C) and are observed to affect PVDF film properties in a similar way: increases in each post-processing parameter promoting similar changes in PVDF properties, i.e, the fraction of electroactive phases, $\beta + \gamma$, varies between 70% and 80%, the degree of crystallinity between 61 and 67% and the $|d_{33}|$ between 8.8 and 13.6 pC/N. Compression post-treatment does not require fine tuning for application since all parameter tested are improved simultaneously.

All processes used in the present work are simple and easily scalable and can be applied industrially making the combination of both techniques (NIPS and thermos-mechanical post-processing) adequate for the large-scale production of electroactive PVDF membranes exhibiting strong piezoelectric behavior.

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